

SHAPING

What aspects does the algorithmic system aim to detect about your emotional state? Can it “say” anything about your emotional state?

YOUR EMOTIONAL STATE

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**Can it influence or alter your
emotional state, such as
transitioning from sadness to
happiness or maintaining
your current state?**

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**Where would you prefer your
emotional state to transition?**

Would you be ok with this?

YOUR EMOTIONAL STATE

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**When considering emotional nuances, like a breakup versus general despair, what specific emotional outcomes do you desire?
For instance, preferring rage over happiness for a certain affective shaping.**

YOUR EMOTIONAL STATE

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**Should the algorithm
optimize for happiness as the
desired emotional state?**

YOUR EMOTIONAL STATE

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How would these transitions differ when focusing on individual versus collective stances? For instance, during a party's "start a jam" session, what insights can be gleaned about the group's collective emotional state?

YOUR EMOTIONAL STATE